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THE ROLE OF GOVERNMENT SUPPORT IN ACCOMPANYING ENTREPRENEURIAL ENTERPRISES TO ACHIEVE INOVATION IN ALGERIA

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Abstract. The research paper aims to highlight the importance of the efforts made by state agencies to improve the ways of success of entrepreneurial enterprises in Algeria, and to focus on the innovation promoting within them in light of modern developments in the economic environment, Descriptive and analytical approaches were used, as well as the statistical approach, as required by the nature of the subject. The study reached in a set of results, the most important of which are: the Algerian government is working to provide all forms of support and accompaniment to small and medium-sized enterprises, particularly in the areas of financial support and technical advice. Algeria has also launched numerous national and international initiatives and programs to promote start-up innovation and support their entrepreneurial way. Despite all this, these businesses still suffer from weak regulatory and legislative frameworks and a lack of awareness of the importance of innovation and technological progress in the fields of finance and business.

Keywords: *accompanying ecosystem, creativity, project financing, young entrepreneurs.*

Rezumat. Lucrarea își propune să evidențieze importanța eforturilor depuse de agențiile statului pentru a îmbunătăți realizările activităților antreprenoriale din Algeria și să se concentreze pe promovarea inovării în cadrul acestora, în lumina evoluțiilor moderne din mediul economic. Au fost utilizate abordări descriptive și analitice, precum și abordarea statistică, așa cum o impune natura subiectului. Studiul a ajuns la un set de rezultate, dintre care cele mai importante sunt: Guvernul algerian depune eforturi pentru a oferi toate formele de sprijin și însoțire întreprinderilor mici și mijlocii, în special în domeniile sprijinului financiar și consultanței tehnice. Algeria a lansat, de asemenea, numeroase inițiative și programe naționale și internaționale pentru a promova inovația în startup-uri și a sprijini demersul lor antreprenorial. În ciuda tuturor acestor lucruri, aceste întreprinderi încă suferă de cadre de reglementare și legislative slabe și de o lipsă de conștientizare a importanței inovării și a progresului tehnologic în domeniile finanțelor și afacerilor.

Cuvinte cheie: *ecosistem însoțitor, creativitate, finanțare de proiecte, tineri antreprenori.*

1. Introduction

Today, entrepreneurship represents great opportunities in the markets, and it also represents the appropriate strategies that are the basis for enterprises seeking to achieve competitive advantages [1]. One of the main drivers of entrepreneurship is the creation of new enterprises, including small and medium enterprises and start-ups, due to their positive impact on their continuity [2]. Most governments focus on making entrepreneurship one of the basic strategies, with the aim of achieving economic growth and sustainable development, with a clear understanding of the factors that drive entrepreneurial enterprises to survive and succeed [3].

Entrepreneurial enterprises are considered a basic symbol in economic and social development, and most societies pay great attention to them, due to their ability to create job opportunities, ensure quality, efficiency and productivity, and they also constitute an important engine for promoting innovation, achieving business ideas and transforming economic structures [4]. In the same context, SMEs seek entrepreneurship to improve emerging competencies or to venture into new, more innovative product areas, and technology-based start-ups are often adept at identifying abundant and new entrepreneurial opportunities [5].

Over the past few years, the subject of business accompaniment has become an important topic in the field of entrepreneurship [6], various forms of accompaniment such as: incubators, government institutions and agencies, and technology parks, create a kind of dynamism, stimulate markets and encourage the creation of new companies, These structures offer a wide range of services: from accommodation to training, financing, coaching, individual and group counselling and guidance services, and play an important role in supporting small and medium-sized enterprises and start-ups and maximizing their chances of survival [7].

Algeria has implemented a series of reforms aimed at supporting entrepreneurship as a social and economic phenomenon; this is evident in the important tasks and roles played by financial and non-financial support agencies and programs, such as providing loans of various types and the ongoing and renewed efforts to provide training and technical support to entrepreneurs, and university graduates [8,9].

The study is based on the hypothesis that the Algerian government is currently helping to shape entrepreneurial intentions and capabilities. The study assumes that support and guidance mechanisms foster entrepreneurial innovation among young entrepreneurs, SME owners, and start-ups managers, facilitate access to financial support, and reduce barriers to project creation.

Our contribution in this research paper is to reveal the role of accompaniment in supporting entrepreneurial enterprises, providing various financial and non-financial assistance to emerging companies, and also to cite various government agencies and programs in Algeria dedicated to supporting young entrepreneurs and project holders and supporting them towards innovation.

2. Entrepreneurial Enterprises in Algeria

The term entrepreneurial enterprises refer to innovative projects and activities, that lead to the introduction of new services and products, and are also viewed as an exploration of pioneering opportunities and new activities [10], Entrepreneurial enterprises mean the presence of entrepreneurial intentions, which are interpreted as the desire to create or develop a new business venture [11].

It can be said that the process of establishing an entrepreneurial enterprise targets everything that is new in terms of innovative goods and services, based on good economic knowledge, or in other words, it is entering into the new economic system, as these institutions aspire towards entrepreneurship related to change and how to expand their activities, It also involves a certain degree of management and direction, and the general pattern of organizing tasks within it has a formal and informal character, and it enjoys the advantages of flexibility in local markets. From another perspective, it can be said that the entrepreneurial project is the work in which Investors have to create their own structures, and make a set of decisions at their level, or find a ready-made structure in which they are prepared, to perform their activities and adapt to it [12]. Entrepreneurship is the ambition of all organizations regardless of their age or size (start-ups, small or medium enterprises), and its importance is reflected in supporting economic growth. It is referred to as a vision of the business opportunities that lie behind the establishment of a new institution, by integrating the knowledge and skills of entrepreneurs, and financial and technical capabilities in an environment characterized by risk and uncertainty [13]. Entrepreneurial firms are those ideas that need financial and non-financial resources, in addition to having legitimacy and market knowledge; they need resources to survive and achieve success and are often described as weak projects in their beginnings. However, entrepreneurs believe in the innovations they create, and the expected value behind their work. In many references, the initial opportunity that entrepreneurial firms exploit is highlighted, with the need to interact, adapt, and transform, while learning new information in the face of uncertainty [14].

Small and Medium Enterprises-Sized (SMEs), Start-upson the Path to Entrepreneurship

There are several factors that make SMEs and start-ups similar in their reliance on entrepreneurship, While SMEs focus on niche and local markets, innovative start-ups aim to innovate and expand globally, this diversity of goals suggests that these companies do not feel threatened by each other and do not suffer from a lack of trust [15]. Small and medium enterprises play a crucial role in all national economies, and many literatures have addressed the fact that these enterprises are the most important part of entrepreneurship, SMEs have low costs, which gives innovative entrepreneurs more efficient organizational structures and streamlined decision-making processes, that enable them to quickly change their operations to take advantage of new opportunities or respond to new challenges [16]. The creation of small and medium enterprises affects any type of business activity, in urban or rural areas, Jobs, growth and investment in SMEs are achieved once the regulatory environment is cleared, strict regulations are not imposed, and the entrepreneurial climate is enhanced and jobs are created [17]. The need to develop entrepreneurship in many economies around the world cannot be denied, as the entrepreneur's ability to innovate helps improve economic growth by developing small and medium enterprises and supporting them with the programs and capabilities they need [18].

Given the situation in Algeria, we see that small and medium enterprises are constantly increasing, meaning that these institutions are showing a great desire to move towards entrepreneurship, as their number in 2017 was approximately 1074503, but this number has increased to reach 2022by 1359803, and the overwhelming percentage belongs to the private sector at the expense of the public sector. This can be explained by the fact that project holders establish their enterprises with private funds or from family and friends, without resorting to public subsidies, and the below Table shows all of this.

Table 1

Evolution of the number of SMEs by Legal nature 2017-2022						
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Private SMEs (1)	1074236	1141602	1193096	1230844	1286140	1359580
Legal persons	609344	643493	671267	689383	720495	762769
natural persons	464892	498109	521829	541461	565645	596811
Liberal professions	222570	237457	247275	252737	262040	272726
Craft activities	242322	260652	274554	228724	303605	324085
Public SMEs (2)	267	261	243	229	225	223
Total	1074503	1141863	1193339	1231073	1286365	1359803

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [19].

As we mentioned earlier, small and medium enterprises are active in many economic activities and fields. According to the Table 2, we see that the services sector comes at the top of the list with 703499 projects, followed by craftsmanship 324085 enterprises, and then the construction and public works sector with 204452 establishments, with acceptable statistics for the industrial and agricultural sectors.

Table 2

Distribution of SMEs by economic sectors						
Sector of activity	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Agriculture	6687	7168	7481	7690	8010	8404
Hydrocarbons, Energy, Mines and related services	2890	2985	3066	3115	3243	3371
Public Works Building and Hydraulics	179326	185137	109170	193964	199331	204452
Manufacturing industries	95010	99938	103693	106121	109991	115992
Services	548268	585983	614375	631459	662185	703499
Craftsmanship	242322	260652	274554	288724	303605	324085
Total	1074503	1141863	1193339	1231073	1286365	1359803

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [19].

Table 3 presents that most small and medium enterprises are located in the eastern regions and states, where 945153 enterprises were recorded in 2022. This is attributed to the capabilities available in the northern region, and the presence of awareness and entrepreneurial culture of the importance of establishing entrepreneurial projects, unlike the southern regions, which experience a kind of deficiency and injustice in the direction towards the entrepreneurial path with 113905 enterprises, due to weak development, which requires more efforts to enhance the establishment of small and medium enterprises.

Table 3

Distribution of SMEs by Areas						
Areas	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
North	424659	794633	830438	856779	894882	945153
Highlands	133177	251007	262340	270736	283416	300745
South	51508	96174	100561	103558	108068	113905
Total	1074503	1141863	1193339	1231073	1286365	1359803

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [19].

The concept of startups and entrepreneurship is a group of people who have the ability to start a business and work on making it grow very quickly, or It is the search for a scalable business model, through which new products, services and innovative ideas are launched, with high income and high potential to change the competition, In many studies, start-ups are viewed from the perspective of using IT innovations and high potential, as they relate to two well-established terms of entrepreneurship: entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial self-efficacy [20]. Its size does not matter because it contributes to development and growth that is higher than large businesses, but the lack of knowledge about start-ups, which is their most important feature, affects the entry of new companies into this field. Among its main factors are economic fragmentation, weak or non-existent entrepreneurship culture, and many studies have proven that intellectual capital and entrepreneurship climate have a positive impact on the establishment and survival of start-ups [3], many scientific research papers have provided clear evidence that entrepreneurial opportunities contribute to the creation of many new businesses and start-up companies with high growth, distinguished performance and competitiveness. They also play an important role for these companies in creating solutions to social, economic and environmental problems, ultimately leading to a positive impact on economic performance and its development [21].

According to the global ranking of the number of start-ups, Algeria ranked 17th in 2024 with 808 start-ups (expressed in Figure 1), taking the lead on the African continent, which is a good position compared to 2020, when it achieved only 41 companies. This means that Algeria is experiencing a qualitative leap in the field of promoting the establishment of start-ups and harnessing all possibilities and means to support their owners. In the same context, the first place went to the United States of America with 83373 companies. At the Arab level, in light of the trend adopted by the Gulf countries towards digitization and innovation, the United Arab Emirates ranked first among the countries of the region with 1404 start-ups.

Figure 1. Number of startups in the world including Algeria in 2024 [22].

Figure 2 shows **Yassir** tops the list of the most successful startups in Algeria, This Company specializes in providing transportation services for the benefit of customers, Despite the intense competition with many companies in the same field, and it achieved approximately \$217 million in 2022. The rest of the arrangement was as follows:

Figure 2. Leading start-ups in Algeria as of 2022, by total funding (in million U.S. dollars) [23].

3. Entrepreneurial Accompaniment and Institutional Support in Algeria

Entrepreneurial Accompaniment is the long-term symbiotic relationship that takes place between the support provider and the person who owns the enterprise or project to be supported, the human factor is the focus of this process, which means that the general basis of support is a technical and psychological approach more than anything else. In general, entrepreneurial enterprises can benefit, through accompaniment, from many forms of institutional support, such as financial support, which is the most important element in the life of any project, strategic support, production and commercial planning, as well as logistical support and benefiting from advisory networks [24]. Entrepreneurial Accompaniment has become a necessity and an important public issue, which would allow enterprises to benefit from a higher survival rate than those that do not receive support, and

facilitate the creation of knowledge and marketing of their entrepreneurial activity, through policies to support the creation of businesses or the transfer of technology, as the industry of entrepreneurial Accompaniment and support has developed tremendously, through the multiplicity of actors, government agencies and even associations [25].

Regarding Algeria's situation in terms of entrepreneurial support, the government has made every effort to develop and grow entrepreneurial enterprises and support them in various ways, The Algerian state has established the Agency for the Development of Small and Medium Enterprises and the Promotion of Innovation by virtue of Executive Decree No. 18-170 of June 26, 2018, amended and supplemented by Executive Decree No. 25-331 of November 22, 2020, The agency is responsible for implementing the policy of developing small and medium enterprises in the field of creating, growing and sustaining these institutions in coordination with the relevant sectors. Its services include providing support and advisory centers as well as business incubators [26]:

- **Support and Consulting Centers.** It provides programs and policies to support SMEs development and sustainability. Table 4 summarizes statistics of these centers in Algeria.

Table 4

Number of enterprises benefiting from Accompaniment at the end of 2022		
Sector of Activity	Number of projects supported	Number of innovative projects
Industry	122	01
Tourism	16	0
Services	60	13
Public Works Building and Hydraulics	22	1
Crafts	29	0
Commerce	2	0
Agriculture	48	1
Renewable Energy	2	0
Environment	4	0
ICT	0	0
Agri-food	15	1
Start-up	2	1
Other services	9	0
Total	331	18

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [19].

- **Business incubators** is an integrated framework that provides environment containing equipment, services, facilities, support mechanisms, consultation and organization, dedicated to helping owners of ideas or newly established enterprises, and managing SMEs. The following table provides important details about local incubation data.

Table 5

Number of enterprises hosted in Incubators at the end of 2022

Sector of Activity	Number of projects hosted	Number of SMEs created	Number of jobs created
Industry	58	26	264
ICT	81	26	40
Renewable Energy	18	7	13
Services	58	27	134
Public Works Building and Hydraulics	16	6	32
Agriculture	8	7	73
Environment, recovery, sorting, recycling, waste treatment	13	1	11
Tourism	1	1	18
Agri-food	16	10	39
Aquaculture	1	1	4
Start-up	8	2	6
Total	278	114	634

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [19].

- Launch of Programme to Support Industrial Diversification and Improve the Business Climate in Algeria, supported by the European Union and the World Bank, and thanks to the renewed involvement of the Algerian authorities (particularly the Ministry of Industry and Mines), the government is trying to accelerate the pace of reforms in order to improve the business climate, the goal being to alleviate the problems and burdens of small and medium-sized enterprises, with the aim of driving the economy and increasing employment opportunities [27].

- The National Consultation Council for the Development of Small and Medium Enterprises was created in order to promote consultation and dialogue between public authorities and SMEs represented by professional associations and organizations, to form a real partnership between the two entities in terms of developing, implementing and monitoring policies set for the development of small and medium enterprises [28].

- The President Abdelmadjid Tebboune also launched the "Algeria Disrupt" program in October 2020, which provides a legal and regulatory framework to encourage start-ups and accelerate their growth, and includes the creation of the Algerian Start-up Fund and the start-up accelerator A-Venture to support innovation and entrepreneurship in Algeria, the objective is to provide start-ups with the resources and support necessary to transform their projects into successes, and create a strong and diversified economy, based on knowledge and new technologies [29].

- The PAD-PME program aims to improve the general framework for the development of small and medium-sized enterprises in Algeria, by providing the necessary technical accompaniment to support and assistance agencies, so that they can provide quality services [26].

- GEN Algeria launched the Women Entrepreneurship Program in 2017 to support women entrepreneurs to move from informal to formal business operations, and enhance their potential for success and sustainability, especially as they face challenges in business growth. The Women Entrepreneurship Program has achieved satisfactory results through its three editions, and has been able to target thousands of women and provide them with entrepreneurial skills and opportunities. Thus, the program has helped create a strong network of women entrepreneurs, generate new cooperation opportunities, create new jobs and contribute to the country's economic growth [30].

- Issuance of Ministerial Resolution No. 1275 dated 09/27/2022, which specifies the procedures for preparing a project thesis to obtain a university degree -a start-up project for higher education students.

- Establishing university incubators pursuant to Correspondence No. 1428 dated 09/29/2022 from the Secretary-General of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research [8].

- The creation of the Entrepreneurship House in higher education institutions (universities and graduate schools), which constitutes a fundamental element in developing entrepreneurial values among students, its mission is to develop the spirit of initiative among students, value the relationship between university institutions and organize events related to the field of entrepreneurship [31].

- The Loan Guarantee Fund was established by Executive Decree No. 02-373 issued on November 11, 2002, It is a public institution with legal personality and financial independence, working to provide guarantees for small and medium-sized enterprises, undertake the follow-up of collection operations for disputed receivables, follow up on the risks arising from the Loan Guarantee Fund, ensure advice and technical assistance to project owners, and ensure receiving information about banks and financial institutions on a regular basis [32].

- By Executive Decree No. 04-14 issued on January 22, 2004, the National Agency for Microcredit Management was created as a special entity subject to the authority of the Prime Minister, enjoying legal personality and financial independence, with branches throughout the national territory, working to support beneficiaries of the microcredit system by consulting and accompanying them in carrying out their activities, in addition to being distinguished by providing different loans without charging any rewards (see Table 6) [33].

Table 6

Credits granted by type of financing at the end of 2022

Type of financing	Number	Share, %	Jobs created
Financing Purchase of Raw Materials	868562	89.89	1261671
Triangular financing "Agency-Bank-promoter"	97740	10.11	151224
Total	966302	100%	1412895

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [34].

- The National Unemployment Insurance Fund was created by Executive Decree No. 94-187 issued on July 6, 1994, It is under the supervision of the Minister in charge of Social Security,

The Fund is concerned with undertaking technical and economic studies for new business creation projects, for the benefit of the unemployed, in cooperation with public employment services, and providing various forms of assistance in order to preserve jobs [35]. The following table indicates the latest data obtained from the Fund's website.

Table 7

Projects funded and employment impact by The Fund					
Number of financial projects	Year 2022		Cumulative as of 12/31/2022		
	Employments prior to start	Total investment financing (million DZD)	Number of financial projects	Employments prior to start	Total investment financing (million DZD)
40	107	214.27	160202	340500	554780.18

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [36].

4. The Algerian Government efforts to establish a culture of innovation

Innovation encompasses all types of business sectors, is defined on the basis of approaches to discovering new products and modern forms of economic organization, and is closely related to entrepreneurship, Innovation is the process of creating new tools to do something, and the methods involved can be classified into 10 types within the categories of business formation, product offering, customer experience, and it is not only related to continuous operational improvements but also to inventions and the use of the latest technological developments [37].

Algeria has developed a set of plans and programs to support innovation, including:

- The "Innovation and Development of Small and Medium Enterprises" project INNODEV is a cooperation program with the German partner, through the German Agency for International Cooperation "GIZ", which aims to enhance the capabilities and sales services directed to them, in order to emerge as innovative, competitive and sustainable small and medium enterprises.

- Creation of the National Innovation Award for Small and Medium Enterprises. By Executive Decree No. 08-323 dated Shawwal 14, 1429 corresponding to October 14, 2008; it is a mechanism to encourage small and medium enterprises to integrate into the dynamic of permanent and continuous innovation, The eleventh (11) edition of the award is currently being organized [26].

- IncubMe is an African business incubator founded in 2018 by Algerian entrepreneurs, aiming to provide the ideal environment for project holders to realize their ideas and create their businesses; IncubMe provides consulting and guidance services, training and coaching courses for entrepreneurs and many recommendations [38].

- Algeria Startup Challenge, the largest startup program, was launched in 2018, the main objective of the program is to create innovative opportunities that bring together institutions, economic actors, innovators, startups and experts, while proposing several solutions resulting from open innovation challenges [39].

- The Algerian Foundation for the Promotion of Entrepreneurship and Support of Startups has launched the annual national program "DZ Excellence Camp", which brings

together talented, hardworking and creative participants from all over the country, is an annual program focused on innovation, creativity and originality in several fields and sectors in Algeria, which is organized in the form of a series of national mini-camps [40].

- Entrepreneurship World Cup: This program gives participants from all over the world, including Algeria, the opportunity to develop their innovative ideas and businesses, with the possibility of presenting them in a global competition to an audience.

- “Innovation Challenge to provide innovative solutions in the field of social economy”. This initiative is part of the United Nations Development Programme, and in agreement with Algeria, aims to eliminate the social and economic challenges facing creative businesses, thus contributing to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals [8].

-The creation of the “Algerian Innovation Fund” worth \$ 80 million, equivalent to about 11 billion dinars, through a partnership between the public accelerator “Algeria Ventures” and the Global Fund for Small Business Assistance. The agreement was signed by Sid Ali Zerouqi (General Manager of Algeria Ventures), and Hubertus van Der Vaart (Investment Director at the Global Fund), in the presence of (the Minister of Knowledge Economy, Startups and Small Businesses), Yacine El Mehdi Walid, This fund is set to operate as an Algerian investment institution under local legislation, with a focus on pumping money into startups [41].

- The World Intellectual Property Organization's Global Innovation Index (GII) is a comprehensive quantitative tool to help policymakers around the world better understand how to stimulate innovative activity, the engine of economic growth and human development. It is calculated based on two sub-indices: creativity inputs and outputs. According to the index in table 8, Algeria ranks 115th out of 132 countries in 2022, a modest ranking for Algeria given the potential and efforts it is making to promote innovation.

Table 8

Evolution of GII Index								
Year	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Ranking	126/141	113/128	108/127	110/126	113/129	121/131	120/131	115/132
Value	24.38	24.46	24.34	23.87	23.98	19.48	19.90	16.70

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [42].

Regarding the sub-indicators summarized in the Table 9 related to innovation, particular reliance was placed on those related to enhancing creativity for entrepreneurial enterprises; the sub-indicators inputs witnessed a kind of stability, starting with the institutions index, which witnessed a noticeable improvement, while the infrastructure index recorded a decline, especially through public infrastructure, As for the sub-indicators that make up the creativity output index, what is noticeable is the improvement that the knowledge and technological output index witnessed during the year 2022, and this after the decline recorded in 2019-2021, also attributed to the improvement in the creative output index through non-creative products.

Table 9

Ranking of Innovation sub-indicators in Algeria

Sub Indicators	2019	2020	2021	2022
Inputs Indicators				
1. Institutions	106	104	104	99
Political Climate	111	110	106	103
Regulatory Environment	109	105	108	105
Business Environment	88	92	92	77
2. Infrastructure	81	100	96	102
ICT	115	114	112	115
Public Infrastructure	10	42	50	61
Energy and Environment	74	79	83	110
3. Market Development	122	130	132	125
Loans	125	129	129	113
Investment	99	130	131	110
Trade and Competitiveness	78	99	115	120
Outputs Indicators				
1. Knowledge and Technological Outputs	113	125	125	118
Knowledge Cration	90	90	94	94
Knowledge Impact	107	119	119	116
Knowledge Dissemination	126	128	125	122
2. Creativity Outputs	117	118	118	109
Creative Goods and Services	111	115	113	98
Intangible Creative Products	125	125	128	120
Online Creations	102	101	114	106

Source: elaborated by authors based on data [43].

5. Conclusions

The research paper explored the importance of government support in encouraging the establishment of entrepreneurial enterprises, supporting their innovation, through various programs and devices provided by the Algerian government. We saw that the state has a clear and explicit direction in developing these enterprises and harnessing all capabilities to help them overcome the challenges of survival and continuity, especially the problem of financing, which is the most prominent obsessional challenge leading to closures and failure.

Algeria has been quick to adopt the idea of entrepreneurship, by supporting and encouraging entry into this type of activity that is witnessing widespread spread in many countries of the world, in an effort to revive the national economy, and strongly instill the

dynamic of development, this has been evident through the trend of establishing projects/institutions, and entering the field of entrepreneurship, with the aim of attracting young people who carry ideas and investment projects.

The study reached a set of valuable findings; the efforts made by Algeria through its government institutions in recent years have played a pivotal role in strengthening the infrastructure of entrepreneurial enterprises, through beneficial support and Accompaniment policies and substantial financial funding such as business incubators, and institutional agencies, this reflects a trend following in the footsteps of strategies employed in developed countries, To support innovation for entrepreneurial enterprises, the state is gradually adopting global best practices by establishing technology hubs, coworking spaces, and strengthening a strong government support network that fosters public-private sector collaboration, Administrative, legal, and financial challenges are among the most significant obstacles facing entrepreneurs in Algeria, However some entrepreneurs have managed to navigate these complexities in innovative ways, such as working with specialized consultants or leveraging state support, their determination to overcome these difficulties has allowed these entrepreneurs to develop their projects and achieve their goals.

Based on the findings, some recommendations can be made regarding the research topic:

- It is essential for the Algerian government and relevant stakeholders to continue their support for innovation and entrepreneurship, by developing more appropriate policies and programs that facilitate the growth and sustainability of entrepreneurial projects.
- Fostering exchanges between entrepreneurial enterprises and relevant stakeholders, and encouraging local and international cooperation, is vital to stimulating innovation and development within the sector.
- Regular monitoring and evaluation of project performance will facilitate continuous learning and improvement; ensure the sustainability of business models, contributing to the long-term viability of the start-ups and SME ecosystem in Algeria.
- Spreading the culture of entrepreneurship among the academic community by organizing scientific events and conferences and incorporating the subject of “entrepreneurship” into various academic training courses.
- Today, entrepreneurs are in dire need of training in the business world, providing skills in a few days is not enough to fully grasp business management, a medium-term approach should be used to acquire basic skills.
- Consideration should also be given to establishing a national information system, databases, and professional organizations capable of conducting real market and technical-economic studies, this will enhance and enrich entrepreneurs' knowledge of the economic environment in general and their markets in particular.

As for the future research, it is possible to delve into the field of financial technology and its role in enhancing the innovative capabilities of entrepreneurial enterprises.

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